

Financial Analysis of Agritourism Operations: A Case Study

S. G. Walke¹ and Atul Kumar²

¹Director, SNG Institute of Management and Research, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

²Associate Professor, Siddhant Institute of Business Management, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

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ABSTRACT

Due to a convergence of global market dynamics, rising costs, and urbanization pressure Indian farmers are enforced to unearth innovative ways of diversification. The main objective of the research was to analyse the financial potential of the Agritourism business and evaluate the results to conclude whether Agritourism can provide an alternative source of income to the farmers for their sustainable development. The study is also aimed at providing authentic research-based information on Agritourism to aspiring farmers to assist them in making the decision of starting up of this new business venture and to help them design their business strategies. The research methodology involved both desk research and field research which was used to depict the concept of Agritourism and the various financial facets that are involved in the successful running of Agritourism. For the field research, unstructured interview was conducted to gather information from the owner of Anand Agritourism, Chicholi Morachi, Pune. The available financial records of the same ATC were analysed to fulfil the objectives of the study. Agri-tourism is a way of attracting tourists to experience a rural and agricultural environment through multiple, participative activities. Tourism always has a multiplier effect and here too it was found that the tourist trips and associate spending made a significant contribution to rural economies and improved quality of life of the farmers. Agritourism is a profitable business with Payback period of fewer than 4 years. The farmers can also sell their farm products directly to the visitors and make more profits as compared to conventional methods of selling their products in the markets because that would involve transportation, brokerage intermediaries and other indirect costs. Agritourism provides an opportunity for the farmers to increase their annual income by rendering diversified services to the visitors, while simultaneously educating the non-farm public about farming and enhancing community participation. The social interaction of the farmer and his family with various kinds of visitors helps them to learn new things, share and exchange their knowledge and experiences and thereby improving their social status and enriching their lives in general. Also Agritourism gives employment to all members of the household, including women, thus making better utilisation of the human resource available with the Agripreneur. From the tourist point of view Agritourism provides them a cost-effective form of experiencing rural culture and recreating their mind, body and soul. The conclusions drawn are only on the basis of one ATC and since the respondent was only the owner of one ATC the data gathered is restricted and this has to be tested and finalised on larger area and large sample size. Agritourism has emerged as one form of alternative enterprise development for a growing number of farmers. By analysing the profitability of the business venture more and more farmers can be motivated to start this business which will lead to improvement in their living standards and upliftment of the rural society. Studies related to Agritourism will help to improve the economic status of our villages and will also lead to the preservation of monuments and places of historical importance. People will become more aware of our cultural heritage and it will also attract the attention of local, state and national authorities towards this often neglected legacy from our past. More targeted empirical

research is required to clearly articulate the economic benefits of Agritourism in India, particularly at state or regional scales. Non-Monetary benefits associated with Agritourism include personal entrepreneurial or lifestyle goals, expansion of farm employment opportunities for family members, preservation of rural lifestyle, and social interaction with guests.

KEYWORDS: Agritourism centre, Agripreneurs, Agritourism NPR, Payback period, Agritourism ROI, Cumulative investment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to uneven rainfall and depleting soil fertility the crop yield has declined and to add to the cause rising prices of commodities have forced the farmers to find alternative sources of income. Agritourism is an increasingly popular form of alternative agriculture enterprise development designed to expand farm income, generally through fuller employment of existing farm resources. Agritourism has provided the farmers with a source of additional income to capitalise on their existing assets.

The existing literature is inconclusive about the importance of Agritourism as a component of farm income. There has been a paradigm shift in the economy from selling the goods and commodities to the selling of services and now to sell off "experiences". By selling experiences we mean that people are willing to pay for experiencing new lifestyles. Due fast pace of urban life people is running to earn more and more money and in the process, they become victims of mental stress and boredom of their routine work. One of the oldest and trusted methods of getting rid of stress is to relax in the midst of nature. Agritourism is an activity that can aid such relaxation and the money which people usually spend on their recreation and entertainment every year gets diverted too much needy pockets of farmers. Apart from this the farmers can also get the share of the amount annually spent on food by people.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Confronted with declining profitability, operators of small farms commonly face the options of exiting agriculture, expanding off-farm employment to supplement household earnings, or developing alternative agricultural enterprises (McGehee, 2007 and Ollenburg and Buckley, 2007).

The United States Department of Agriculture's Sustainable Agriculture Research and Education (SARE) defines sustainable agriculture as an activity that promotes environmental stewardship, generates an acceptable level of income, and maintains stable farm families and communities (SARE, 2002). All sustainable agriculture research promotes the three foundational guidelines of environmental health, economic profitability and social/economic equity all fostered through the development of Agritourism.

Beyond noting definitional challenges, over the past two decades, various authors have commented on the lack of a coherent and comprehensive body of literature on Agritourism development and its impact on farm operations (Busby and Rendle, 2000; Opperman, 1995 and Tew and Barbieri, 2012). Income generation and diversification potential has been found to be a primary motivation for Agritourism development on farms (McGehee and Kim, 2004 and Schilling *et al.*, 2006); however, some studies have found, perhaps paradoxically, that Agritourism income tends to be relatively insubstantial in relation to total farm income (Busby and Rendle, 2000; Hjalager, 1996; Opperman, 1995 and Sharpley and Vass, 2006). Tew and Barbieri (2012) therefore deem the literature inconclusive in terms of the economic benefits of Agritourism.

3. RESEARCH PROBLEM, OBJECTIVES AND HYPOTHESES OF THE RESEARCH

3.1. Research problem

Literature review, discussions with an expert makes it easy for us to identify the Research problem that

- Does this business promise to deliver large enough revenue relative to the investment required?

- What would be the payback period for the investment?
- Are there seasonal fluctuations in the sales pattern for a year?

3.2. Objectives of the research

The main objective of the research was to do the financial analysis of Agritourism operation in Pune. The initial idea behind the research was gaining insight into the profitability and pattern of cash flows to assess the Payback period. After reviewing the relevant literature, specific objectives were formed to help define the study, which in turn assisted in composing the questionnaire for data collection. In order to fill a broad void in current research, other complementary objectives pursued in this study were:

- To identify and various costs incurred in operating an ATC.
- To analyse the initial startup cost or Agritourism capital employed with respect to the Agritourism net profit to arrive at Agritourism ROI.
- To find out the Agritourism Payback period.
- To understand the pattern of annual sales and profitability during a year for the ATC.

3.3. Hypotheses

The researchers developed the hypotheses to be investigated and tested statistically in order to be accepted or rejected with the purpose of developing findings and conclusions. The hypotheses are:

- **H₁:** Agritourism a financially viable co-activity for the farmers in Pune.
- **H₂:** There is significant fluctuation in the month wise profitability for the Agritourism centre.
- **H₃:** The time taken for the Payback period is < 5 yrs.

4. METHODOLOGY

The research methodology involved both desk research and field research which was used to depict the concept of Agritourism and the various financial facets that are involved in the successful running of Agritourism. To fulfil the objective of this research Sample element/unit is selected by following ways: The Agripreneurs were selected by the convenience sampling method. The researcher has discussed with the owner, farmer about his experience of running Agritourism at Chincholi Morachi, in Pune. The Investment and net profit figures for the ATC from the year of starting business to 2014 were as depicted in table 1:

Year	2011	2012	2013	2014
Agritourism Investment	Rs 2,00,000	Nil	Rs 3,00,000	Nil
Agritourism Sales Revenue	Rs 1,00,000	Rs 1,50,000	Rs 2,50,000	Rs 4,50,000
Agritourism operational expenses	Rs 20,000	Rs 35,000	Rs 75,000	Rs 1,80,000
Agritourism Net Profit	Rs 80,000	Rs 1,15,000	Rs 1,75,000	Rs 2,70,000

Month	Agritourism Sales revenue (Rs)	Agritourism Cost (Rs)	Agritourism Net Profit(Rs)
January 2014	26,500	10600	15,900
February 2014	22,200	8880	13,320
March 2014	21,300	8520	12,780
April 2014	11,000	4400	6,600
May 2014	10,600	4240	6,360
June 2014	8,400	3360	5,040
July 2014	42,600	17040	25,560
August 2014	48,800	19520	29,280
September 2014	58,600	23440	35,160
October 2014	67,000	26800	40,200
November 2014	62,500	25000	37,500
December 2014	70,500	28200	42,300
Total	4,50,000	1,80,000	2,70,000

The data was analysed using the following statistical tools:

- Standard deviation, mean and coefficient of variation is calculated for the Agritourism Net profit ratio, Agritourism Return on capital employed, Monthwise Agritourism NPR for year 2014 and for Agritourism Cumulative ROI.
- Dupont analysis (Return on Investment) is done for cumulative profit, sales and investment data.
- The Payback period is calculated using cumulative profit and investment data.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Year	2011	2012	2013	2014
ANPR	80%	76.66%	70%	60%
Statistical analysis: Standard Deviation = 7.636536, Mean = 71.665, Coefficient of Variation = 10.655 %				

From table 3, we can easily, make out that the Agritourism NPR has shown a continuous decline from year 2011 to the year 2014 which are not favourable signs for the business, but the good part is that the coefficient of variation is 10.65% which is quite low. This implies that the relative variability in Agritourism NPR is very less and the mean value is found at 71.66% which is a good figure for the business.

Year	2011	2012	2013	2014
AROCE	40%	57.5%	35%	54%
Statistical analysis: Standard Deviation = 9.376667, Mean = 46.625, Coefficient of Variation = 20.110				

Analysis of Agritourism ROCE reveals that the ratio shows fluctuating trend as it increases in 2011, then it drops down in 2013 and again increases in 2014. The average Agritourism ROCE ratio is 46.625%, which is a healthy figure for an innovative business like Agritourism. The coefficient of variation is 20.11 which means that they are acceptable relative variability in the ratio which is good for the health of the business.

Month	Jan-14	Feb-14	Mar-14	Apr-14	May-14	Jun-14	Jul-14	Aug-14	Sep-14	Oct-14	Nov-14	Dec-14
MANPR	52.45%	54.05%	53.80%	48.90%	54.71%	61.19%	64.22%	60.04%	63.75%	61.49%	59.96%	61.87%
Standard Deviation = 4.784967, Mean = 58.03583, Coefficient of Variation = 8.24 %												

The coefficient of variation is very low at 8.24%, which means that there is no significant relative variability in the Net profit margin. Although the sales figures are low for the first half of the year and high sales are achieved during the second half of the year, but the overall profit margin has been maintained by the Agripreneur. H_2 is therefore rejected.

Year	Investment	Revenue	Cost	Profit
2011	Rs 2,00,000	Rs 1,00,000	Rs 20,000	Rs 80,000
2012	Rs 2,00,000	Rs 2,50,000	Rs 55,000	Rs 1,95,000
2013	Rs 5,00,000	Rs 5,00,000	Rs 1,30,000	Rs 3,70,000
2014	Rs 5,00,000	Rs 9,50,000	Rs 3,10,000	Rs 6,40,000

5.1. Dupont Analysis to calculate cumulative Agritourism ROI

5.1.1. The year 2011

Agritourism ROI can be expressed as the product of two ratios namely Agritourism profit margin and Agritourism capital turnover. For the year 2011, the Agritourism profit margin was 80% and Agritourism capital turnover was only 0.5 which was low due to which overall Agritourism ROI was only 40% for the first year of operation.

Cumulative Agritourism ROI	=	$\frac{\text{Cumulative Agritourism Net Profit}}{\text{Cumulative Agritourism sales}} * 100$	*	$\frac{\text{Cumulative Agritourism sales}}{\text{Cumulative Agritourism Capital Employed}}$
	=	$\frac{Rs\ 80,000}{Rs\ 1,00,000} * 100$	*	$\frac{Rs\ 1,00,000}{Rs\ 2,00,000}$
	=	80% * 0.5		
	=	40%		

5.1.2. The year 2012

Cumulative Agritourism ROI	=	$\frac{\text{Cumulative Agritourism Net Profit}}{\text{Cumulative Agritourism sales}} * 100$	*	$\frac{\text{Cumulative Agritourism sales}}{\text{Cumulative Agritourism Capital Employed}}$
	=	$\frac{Rs\ 1,95,000}{Rs\ 2,50,000} * 100$	*	$\frac{Rs\ 2,50,000}{Rs\ 2,00,000}$
	=	78% * 1.25		
	=	97.5%		

For the year 2012, the Agritourism profit margin was 78% and Agritourism capital turnover was 1.25. It is evident that Agritourism profit margin was decreased by 2% as compared to previous years, but its effect was counterbalanced and overcome by a major increase in the Agritourism capital turnover resulting in an overall increase in the Agritourism ROI to 97.5 %.

5.1.3. The year 2013

Cumulative Agritourism ROI	=	$\frac{\text{Cumulative Agritourism Net Profit}}{\text{Cumulative Agritourism sales}} * 100$	*	$\frac{\text{Cumulative Agritourism sales}}{\text{Cumulative Agritourism Capital Employed}}$
	=	$\frac{Rs\ 3,70,000}{Rs\ 5,00,000} * 100$	*	$\frac{Rs\ 5,00,000}{Rs\ 5,00,000}$
	=	74% * 1		
	=	74.0%		

During the year 2013, the Agritourism profit margin was 74 % and Agritourism capital turnover was 1. It is evident that both the ratios have shown a decrease which resulted an overall decrease in the Agritourism ROI to 74%.

5.1.4. The year 2014

Cumulative Agritourism ROI	=	$\frac{\text{Cumulative Agritourism Net Profit}}{\text{Cumulative Agritourism sales}} * 100$	*	$\frac{\text{Cumulative Agritourism sales}}{\text{Cumulative Agritourism Capital Employed}}$
	=	$\frac{Rs\ 6,40,000}{Rs\ 9,50,000} * 100$	*	$\frac{Rs\ 9,50,000}{Rs\ 5,00,000}$
	=	67.36% * 1.9		
	=	127.984%		

For the year 2014 Agritourism profit margin was 67.36 % and Agritourism capital turnover was 1.9. Again, it is found that although the Agritourism profit margin has shown a decreasing trend, its effect is overcome by an almost twofold increase in the Agritourism capital turnover and overall Agritourism ROI is increased to 127.984%. As suggested by Dupont overall ROI can be improved by improving on either of the two ratios and the applicability of this concept is clearly visible in this case study as the Agritourism profit margin has shown a continuous decreasing trend but the Agripreneur is able to maintain high Agritourism ROI by working a high Agritourism capital turnover ratio.

It is observed that Cumulative ROI shows a fluctuating trend as it first increases in 2011, then decreases in 2012 and again increases in 2014. The average is maintained at 84.87 % and the coefficient of variation is 37.95%, which signifies that there is acceptable relative variability in the Cumulative ROI.

From the above calculations, it is evident that Agripreneur has recovered his total capital investment in the 4 years of its operation and has earned 27.984% more than his capital employed to date. Overall, it can be concluded that Agritourism is a financially viable co-activity which gives extra income to the farmers. Hence H_1 is accepted.

Year	Cumulative ROI
2011	40%
2012	97.5%
2013	74%
2014	127.984%
Standard Deviation = 32.2095, Mean = 84.871, Coefficient of Variation= 37.95 %	

5.2. Calculating the time period for the payback period

The above calculation shows that the financial Payback period lies between the 3rd and 4th years.

$$\text{Time taken to breakeven} = 3 + 130/270 = 3.48 \text{ yrs}$$

Therefore H_3 is accepted as the time period to Payback period is less than 5 yrs. The Payback period could have been achieved at the starting of 3rd year, but due to additional investment of Rs 3,00,000 on new assets decreased the cumulative ROI.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The case study of ATC reveals that the Agritourism business is having the potential of generating considerable profits for the ATC owner. The Payback period can be achieved in 3-4 years of operations. There is a seasonal fluctuation in the business income and major part of the annual revenue is received during the rain and the winter season, i.e. from July to December.

The first half of the year, i.e. from January to June does not contribute majorly to the annual revenue earned. Especially the summer period of May and June accounts for least sales, but overall profitability can be maintained by minimising the fixed costs and using only the resources with variable cost.

The following recommendations are provided for individual Farm owners who are interested in developing the new Agritourism centre:

- Agritourism is a financially viable co-activity which can provide them with extra income.
- Agritourism is a secondary activity for the farmers which can make maximum utilization of their available resources.
- The Normally Payback period can be achieved in 3-4 years, so the ATC owners should patiently give time to the business to nurture.
- It is advisable that investment should be made periodically in small installments and as per the requirements that arise in due course of business. Making huge investments at one go may not yield desired results.

7. REFERENCES

1. Busby, G. and Rendle, S. (2000), "The transition from tourism on farms to farm tourism", *Tourism Management*, Vol. 21, Issue 6, pp. 635-642.
2. Hjalager, A. M. (1996), "Agricultural diversification into tourism: Evidence of a European Community development programme", *Tourism Management*, Vol. 17, Issue 2, pp. 103-111.
3. McGehee, N. and Kim, K. (2004), "Motivation for agritourism entrepreneurship", *Journal of Travel Research*, Vol. 43, Issue 2, pp. 161-170.
4. Mcgehee, Nancy Gard (2007), "An Agritourism Systems Model: A Weberian Perspective", *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, Vol. 15, No. 2, pp. 111-224.
5. Oppermann, M. (1995), "Holidays on the farm: A case study of German hosts and guests", *Journal of Travel Research*, Vol. 34, Issue 1, pp. 63-67.

6. Sharpley, R. and Vass, A. (2006), Tourism, farming and diversification: An attitudinal study”, *Tourism Management*, Vol. 27, Issue 5, pp. 1040-1052.
7. Tew, Christine and Barbieri, Carla (2012), “The Perceived Benefits of Agritourism: The Providers Perspective”, *Tourism Management*, Vol. 33, No.1, pp. 215-224.

ABOUT THE AUTHOR (S)

Dr. S. G. Walke is B.Pharm., MBA, SET and Ph.D. He is currently working as a Director in S. N. G. Institute of Management and Research, Rajgurunagar, approved by AICTE, New Delhi, Govt. of Maharashtra and affiliated to the Savatribai Phule Pune University, Pune. He is having more than 17 years of academic and industrial experience. Symbiosis International University awarded a Ph.D. to him in February 2014 after successful completion of research work on the “Study of Agritourism Industry in Maharashtra”. He is Editor in Chief of the biannual Research journal titled “National Journal of Research in Marketing, Finance and HRM” title verified by RNI and bearing ISSN no 2455-5398. He is Chief Consultant for Anand Agri Tourism Center, Morachi Chincholi. He is also contributing to the Solar Energy field by shouldering the responsibility as the chief advisor to New Solar Technology, central Govt. (MNRE) approved organization, Pune. He has presented and/or published number of Research papers in varied International & National Seminars/Conferences and can be reached at krishnawalke@yahoo.co.in.

Dr. Atul Kumar is B.Sc., MBA, M.Phil., PGDIB and Ph.D. He is currently working as a deputy director and associate professor at Siddhant Institute of Business Management, Pune, Maharashtra, which is approved by AICTE, New Delhi, Govt. of Maharashtra and affiliated to the Savatribai Phule Pune University, Pune.